

ASSESSING WOMEN PARTICIPATION IN LIVELIHOOD ACTIVITIES FOR POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN THE NIGER DELTA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RIVERS AND IMO STATES, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study assessed women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in the Niger Delta: A comparative study of Rivers and Imo States, Nigeria. Three specific objectives included to: describe the social economic characteristics of women participating in livelihood activities, determine the level of women participation, and identify the constraints to women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in Rivers and Imo States. Descriptive survey design was adopted to examine a cross section of women in livelihood activities in the area. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were adopted to select four hundred and fourteen (414) women for the study. Questionnaire instrument mostly designed in 'Yes/No' and in a Likert type rating scales were used to elicit information from the respondents. Descriptive statistics such as percentage, arithmetic mean and weighted mean scores were used to analyze the data. Z - Test was the inferential statistics employed to test the hypotheses at 5% significant level. The findings showed that majority of the respondents were married (52.66%), middle age adult women in their prime life of 40 years old. The findings identified crop farming ($\bar{X} = 3.73$), politics ($\bar{X} = 3.63$), trading on agricultural produce ($\bar{X} = 3.62$), food vending and civil service ($\bar{X} = 3.55$), livestock farming and processing of foods ($\bar{X} = 3.53$), fashion and designing ($\bar{X} = 3.51$) and trading on non-agricultural produce ($\bar{X} = 3.45$) among others as the most livelihood activities that women in the study areas participated highly. Finally, the result showed in the order of seriousness that unavailability of farm land to

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women ($\bar{X} = 3.53$), inability to access credits ($\bar{X} = 3.42$), indiscriminate changes in government policies ($\bar{X} = 3.39$), and poor health and lack of power to make decisions ($\bar{X} = 3.35$), among others constitute the first ten most serious constraints to women participation in livelihood activities in the area. The tests of significance in this study revealed no significant difference between the livelihood operations of the women in the two states. The study recommended that: women should be supported by the three tiers of government to actively participate in livelihood activities in the area; assets of land, credits, electricity and extension services should be made available and accessible to women in the study areas by government and non-governmental organizations operating in the areas; and the women should be determined to form themselves into functional cooperative societies for the purpose of raising and using money mutually for their economic growth and development, among others.

Introduction

Poverty is one of the most lasting challenges of the 21st century, with a lopsided impact on women, a phenomenon often described as the "feminization of poverty." Worldwide, women represent a significant proportion of the rural poor, yet they perform the bulk of agricultural and domestic labour (FAO, 2023). In Nigeria, in spite of being the leading economy in Africa, poverty levels keep soaring, with recent data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) indicating that over 133 million Nigerians are multidimensionally poor. Within this demographic, women in rural and peri-urban areas are particularly helpless owing to systemic barriers to land ownership, credit facilities, and formal education (World Bank, 2024). Modern development discussion emphasizes that for poverty alleviation

programmes to be effective, they must be grounded in the active participation of the target group. In the Niger Delta, various government agencies (such as the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), Agricultural Development Programme (ADP)) and the International Oil Companies (IOCs) have introduced empowerment programmes, yet poverty remains persistent. This suggests a potential gap in the assessment of how women actually participate in and benefit from these livelihood pathways.

Participation is not just about being 'beneficiaries' but about having agency in the design and execution of livelihood interventions. It is the act of taking part in decision-making processes and activities or events that will enable people improve upon themselves or the society. Amugo and Odinwa

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(2022) stated that participation is an act or series of acts by which the citizens have the opportunity to influence the sharing of benefits or losses, which may be upon them or upon those people they represent. Odinwa (2019) recorded that participation is a process of playing active though not necessarily direct roles in community decisions, knowledge of local issues, attendance at public meetings, related attempt to influence proposed measures thorough independent and group actions, but belonging to committees and making financial and other necessary contributions towards community programmes. The conceptualization of participation as stated above implies that there must be a genuine and sincere desire on the part of a people, as an independent and social group to be fully involved in development or economic exercise for healthy living.

Women are essential to family and community development in developing countries. In Nigeria, they perform very important duties in national development. Beyond the natural duties of procreation and caring for the young, they contribute in no small measures in agricultural production and rural development. Nseabasi (2015) confirmed this by saying that the role of women in rural development was mainly in the agricultural sector. The responsibility of providing for the families' upkeep originally was on the heads of the families, who most times, was the husbands. Over time, the burden of taking care of the families' upkeep financially had become too heavy for the men. The economic hardship in the rural areas had made the situation worse to the extent that most women had taken up the

responsibility of providing for their families due to either the loss of their spouses or the inability of the men to meet up with their responsibilities. Households' over-reliance on single source of income from the heads of the families (husbands) had brought untold level of hardship to the families especially the women and children (Pur et al., 2016). Consequently, women had to venture into various livelihood activities to enable them generate income to meet with households' necessities.

Livelihood activities refer to the ways which may be economic, social or environmental in nature through which individuals or families make a living, meet their basic needs and improve their wellbeing (Vargas-Lundius & Ypeij, 2012). They include activities that a man attempts to anchor the fundamental necessities of life, such as food, water, shelter and clothing. A person's livelihood involves 'the capacities, resources (material and social) and activities for a means of living (United Nations Development Programme, 2010). International Centre for Development Oriented Research in Agriculture (ICRA, 2012) considers livelihood activities to be making a living or, in other words, producing income. It additionally envelops long term objectives such as food security, giving a home, health, security from all types of sudden events, supportability and capacity to settle on choices that influence the lives of people concerned. A livelihood is said to be sustainable just in the event that it can adapt to and recuperate from pressure and shocks, keep up or upgrade its abilities and resources now and later on without undermining the regular asset base (Silva, 2013). In the face of economic drought in

Nigeria, women in the Niger Delta have engaged in various livelihood activities ranging from petty trading, artisanal food processing (such as cassava and fish smoking), and small-scale livestock rearing to vocational crafts and informal micro-finance (Erondu, 2015).

However, the extent to which these activities actually translate into sustainable poverty alleviation remains a subject of intense debate. Factors such as limited access to modern technology, poor market linkages, and cultural constraints often limit the "scaling up" of these female-led enterprises (Ajadi et al., 2015). While many studies generalize the poverty situation in Nigeria, there is a lack of recent and comparative empirical data on how women's livelihood activities differ across specific states in the Niger Delta hence the need for this study in order to provide a localized lens to understand the differences between the two states in terms of poverty alleviation activities among women. Therefore, the study seeks to:

- i. Describe the socio-economic characteristics of the women participating in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in Rivers and Imo States.
- ii. Determine the level of women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in the areas of study.
- iii. identify the constraints to women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in the two states

To further direct the study two null hypotheses were stated thus:

Ho₁: Levels of women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in the two states do not differ significantly.

Ho₂: The constraints to women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in the two states do not differ significantly.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Rivers and Imo States of the Niger Delta region in Nigeria. Both states face challenges related to environmental degradation, infrastructure development, and security. Rivers State has a female population of approximately 2,525,690, accounting for 48.6% of the total population, while the female population in Imo State is estimated at 3.1 million (Naijapedia (2022)). Women in both states dominated the informal workforce, making up over 50% of the informal labor force and contributing significantly to the economy. However, women in both states are underrepresented in legislative positions. Rivers State was considered in this study as one of the core Niger Delta States and Imo State was taken from the non-core Niger Delta States (Wifa, 2008), for a fair comparison of the livelihood activities undertaken by the women in these areas to reduce poverty.

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. Descriptive survey, according to Odinwa et al. (2023), includes asking questions, gathering and analyzing data from purportedly representative members of the population at a single point in time with a view to resolve the current situation of that population with respect to one or more variables under examination.

The study made use of multistage, purposive and simple random sampling procedures to gather the sample. Firstly, Rivers and Imo States were purposively selected from the nine

states in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. These selected states fall into the two areas known as the 'core' and 'non-core' Niger Delta States (Wifa, 2008). Secondly, three local government areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each state making a total of six (6) LGAs. Thirdly, three communities were randomly selected from each LGA to obtain eighteen (18) communities. Finally, simple random sampling procedure was employed in sampling 23 women (respondents) of different status from each of the selected 18 communities to give a total of 69 respondents per LGA and which altogether made up the sample size of four hundred and fourteen (414) respondents from the selected six (6) LGAs. Questionnaire designed in 'yes' and 'no' options, and in a four-point Likert type rating scale was reliably used to elicit information from the respondents on the specific objectives of the study. This study adopted the descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze data collected from the field. The descriptive statistics such as percentage and arithmetic mean was used to analyze the socio-economic characteristics of the women participating in livelihood activities. While objectives 2 and 3 were analyzed using weighted mean scores derived from the Likert-type rating scales. The four points were added together and divided by four ($4+3+2+1 = 10/4$) to obtain 2.50 as the critical mean. Therefore, any variable with mean < 2.50 was rejected, while any variable with mean ≥ 2.5 was accepted for and used for decision. H_{01} and H_{02} were tested using Z-Test at 5% alpha level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics of women participating in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in Rivers and Imo States

The findings on the socio economic characteristics of women participating in livelihood activities in the Niger Delta Region (Rivers and Imo States, Table 1) showed that the majority of the respondents were middle adult women in their prime age of 40 years old and that majority of them (52.66%) were married and followed by the widowed population (20.53%) which was an addition to the married population in the area. The age and marital factors of the women involved in livelihood activities in the Niger Delta as unveiled by the study are copious advantages for indulging actively in economic and social activities since the middle adults of any sex occupy and drive the scientific, economic and social circles of most developed economy.

The results indicated that the respondents from both states were educated since (52.42% and 30.41%) of them had secondary and tertiary education respectively. Though, the enlightened women were slightly more in Imo State (97.10%) than in Rivers State (84.54%). The finding is a pointer that the women in both states are enlightened and can execute meaningful ventures that they have the capacity to carry out and it supports the study of Erondu *et al*, (2015) and Amugo (2021) whose findings revealed that over 78% and 87% of the plantain traders and farmers in Bayelsa and Kaduna States respectively had formal education and as

such, have high tendency to adapt to new innovations that will support their livelihood.

Also, a mean farm size of 0.68 hectare and a mean household size of five (5) persons per household were unfolded from the study. These imply a small farm size and a moderate household size for women participating in livelihood activities in the study areas. These findings are revealing and can provoke engagements that may help the growth of the family. The findings support the work of Oladeji et al, (2012) who reported that a moderately and fairly large household size dominates the rural people in Nigeria and that its implication is that members of the household may serve as sources of labour and also in meeting the economic demand and food security for the members.

As for years of experience in livelihood activities engaged by the women of both states, the result showed a mean years of experience of nine (9) years, a monthly income of seventy thousand, two hundred and ninety-seven naira and ten kobo (₦70,297.10), and that startup capital of the women were mostly self source (58.70%). These findings especially the monthly income and the source of startup capital in this study

may be the reasons for the mass poverty of the women in both states and in the Niger Delta and portrays their inability to participate in meaningful livelihood activities. This supports the position of Odinwa et al, (2016) for reporting that ‘agricultural productions and most economic activities in Nigeria have been in the hands of small scale women farmers who are characterized by the use of local inputs and poverty’. Also, Amugo (2021) remarked that what characterizes farm households and their members in developing countries like Rivers and Imo States in Nigeria is that they are typically poor.

About contact with extension agents the result showed that majority of the respondents (86%) did not have contact at all with the extension agents. This finding, zero contact of women with extension agents is a serious gap and may be a pointer to weak participation of women in livelihood activities in the Niger Delta Region. This finding was in line with Keremah and Odinwa (2023) who reported that it is frequent and regular extension contacts with the rural farmers that have optimistic effect on the adoption of meaningful technologies and performance by farmers.

Table.1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Women Participating in Livelihood Activities in the Niger Delta Region (Rivers and Imo States)

Variables	Rivers n = (f)	State 207 (%)	Imo n = (f)	State 207 (%)	Mean/%
Age					
20 - 29	28	13.53	49	23.67	
30 - 39	76	36.71	68	32.85	
40 - 49	56	27.05	54	26.09	40 Years
50 - 59	43	20.77	23	11.11	

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60 - 69	4	1.93	13	6.28	
70 and above	0	0	0	0	
Marital Status					
Single	40	19.32	24	11.59	15.46
Married	86	41.55	132	63.77	52.66
Widow/er	50	24.15	35	16.91	20.53
Divorced	31	14.98	16	7.73	11.35
Level of Education					
No Formal education	5	2.42	0	0	01.21
Primary education.	27	13.04	6	2.90	07.97
Secondary	107	51.69	110	53.14	52.42
Tertiary	68	32.85	91	43.96	30.41
Farm Size (Hectare)					
0.1- 0.5ha	119	57.49	130	62.80	
0.6-1.0ha	33	15.94	60	28.99	
1.1-1.5ha	17	8.21	8	3.86	0.68ha
1.6-2.0ha	19	9.18	6	2.90	
2.1 and above	19	9.18	3	1.45	
Household Size (number)					
1- 4 Persons	91	43.96	124	59.90	
5-8 Persons	95	45.89	55	26.57	5 Persons
9-12 Persons	13	6.28	24	11.59	
13-16 persons	0	0	4	1.93	
17 persons and above	8	3.86	0	0	
Years of Experience					
1-5 Years	51	24.64	43	20.77	
6-10 Years	94	45.41	98	47.34	9 Years
11-15 Years	46	22.22	23	11.11	
16 Years and above	16	7.73	43	20.77	

Monthly

Income (₦)

< 50,000	99	47.83	124	59.90	
50,000	64	30.92	61	29.45	
99,000					
100,000	44	21.26	22	10.63	70,297.10
199,000					

Source of Startup capital

Self	116	56.04	127	61.35	58.70
Relatives	63	30.43	46	22.22	26.33
Friends	1	0.48	8	3.86	02.17
Thrift saving	4	1.93	1	0.48	01.21
Money lenders	0	0	1	0.48	00.24
Banks	4	1.93	22	10.63	06.28
Cooperatives	11	5.31	2	0.97	03.14

Regularity of contact with Ext. Agent

None	187	90.34	169	81.64	86.00
Weekly	4	1.93	17	8.21	05.07
Biweekly	4	1.93	0	0	00.97
Monthly	0	0	4	1.93	00.97
Bimonthly	4	1.93	11	5.31	03.62
Quarterly	8	3.86	6	2.90	03.38

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Where f = frequency, % = percent

Level of Women Participation in Livelihood Activities in the Niger Delta Region

Results of the level of women participation in livelihood activities in the Niger Delta Region as shown in Table 2 indicated in the degree of participation that: Crop farming with the grand mean of ($\bar{X} = 3.22$), food vending ($\bar{X} = 3.14$), trading on agricultural produce ($\bar{X} = 3.10$) and processing of foods ($\bar{X} = 3.02$) were the most livelihood activities that women in Rivers and

Imo States participated highly, followed by livestock farming ($\bar{X} = 2.99$), trading on non-agricultural produce ($\bar{X} = 2.96$), fashion and designing ($\bar{X} = 2.95$) and fishing ($\bar{X} = 2.89$) among other measured livelihood activities in this study. All these livelihood activities as showcased by the findings are basic economic activities in both farm and non-farm sectors that most rural and urban women participate to help in family income and well being. This claim is supported by Odoh and Nwibo (2016)

who noted that non-farm income activities include all economic activities in rural areas except agriculture, livestock, fishing and hunting. Hence, it includes activities like processing, marketing, manufacturing, etc., in rural communities.

However, the result also showed that women in both states participated very low in motor cycling and clay pot making with equal grand mean of ($\bar{X} = 2.06$), commercial driving operation ($\bar{X} = 2.11$), traditional birth attendant ($\bar{X} = 2.20$) and computer center ($\bar{X} = 2.30$) among other livelihood activities. The women participation in these aspects of livelihood

activities as the findings showcased could stem from the fact that those activities are masculine in nature and more technical for women to indulge in like motor cycling, clay pot making, commercial driving and computer operations. Generally, the results showed that women in Imo State participated more in most of the livelihood activities than their counterpart in Rivers State except in fishing (Rivers: $\bar{X} = 3.14$, Imo: $\bar{X} = 2.65$), processing of foods (Rivers: $\bar{X} = 3.08$, Imo: $\bar{X} = 2.95$) and food vending (Rivers: $\bar{X} = 3.15$, Imo: $\bar{X} = 3.13$) that Rivers women participated higher than the Imo women.

Table 2: Level of Women Participation in Livelihood Activities in the Niger Delta Region

	Rivers	State	Imo	State	Grand		
Participation in Livelihood Activities	Weighted Score n = 207	Mean \bar{X}	Weighted Score n = 207	Mean \bar{X}	Total Score N = 414	Grand Mean \bar{X}	Remark
Crop Farming	634	3.06	701	3.39	1335	3.22	High
Livestock Farming	616	2.96	620	3.00	1236	2.99	High
Fishing	650	3.14	548	2.65	1198	2.89	High
Processing of foods	638	3.08	611	2.95	1249	3.02	High
Food vending	652	3.15	648	3.13	1300	3.14	High
Trading on agricultural produce	626	3.02	658	3.18	1284	3.10	High
Trading on non-agricultural produce	572	2.76	654	3.16	1226	2.96	High
Fashion and Designing	543	2.62	677	3.27	1220	2.95	High
Hair making	514	2.48	668	3.23	1182	2.86	High
Mat making	439	2.12	558	2.70	997	2.41	Low
Bead making	455	2.20	577	2.79	1032	2.49	Low
Clay pot making	376	1.82	477	2.30	853	2.06	Low
Paid labour service on agricultural production	516	2.49	530	2.56	1046	2.53	High

Paid labour service on non-agricultural production	500	2.42	550	2.66	1050	2.54	High
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	486	2.35	423	2.04	909	2.20	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	462	2.23	547	2.64	1009	2.44	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	458	2.21	548	2.65	1006	2.43	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	462	2.23	513	2.48	975	2.36	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	458	2.21	495	2.39	953	2.30	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	398	1.92	474	2.29	872	2.11	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	404	1.95	450	2.17	854	2.06	Low
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	534	2.58	623	3.01	1157	2.79	High
Traditional attendant Massaging Phone (Recharge cards sales) Phone (Accessories) Computer center Commercial operation Motor cycling Civil service Politics	578	2.79	588	2.84	1166	2.82	High
Cumulative Mean		2.51		2.76		2.64	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Decision Mean = 2.50

The z-test result (Table 3) on the level of women participation in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation in the two states showed a (z-cal = -9.37) and a (z-tab = 1.96) at probability level less than 0.05%. Since z-calculated is less than z-tabulated, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) which states that the level of participation of women in livelihood activities for poverty

alleviation in the two states do not differ significantly was accepted, implying that the level of participation of women in livelihood activities in both states do not differ significantly and a proof that they are facing equal challenges that relate to environmental degradation, infrastructure development, poverty and security.

Table 3: z-test Result on the Level of Women Participation in Livelihood Activities in the Niger Delta Region

Source	N	Mean	df	Variance/Sd	z-cal	z- tab	Remark
Rivers	207	57.84	512	189.96/13.78	-9.37	1.96	NS
Imo	207	64.32		205.21/14.33			
Total	414						

Source: Field Survey, 2025

NS - means Not significant at P > 0.05%

Constraints to Women’s Participation in Livelihood Activities in the Rivers and Imo States

The findings in this case, revealed in the order of seriousness that: Unavailability of farm land to women with a grand mean of ($\bar{X} = 3.53$), ban on importation of economic goods ($\bar{X} = 3.44$),

inability to access credits ($\bar{X} = 3.42$), indiscriminate changes in government policies ($\bar{X} = 3.39$), poor health and lack of power to make decisions with equal grand mean ($\bar{X} = 3.35$), high rate of inflation ($\bar{X} = 3.34$), lack of social capital/network ($\bar{X} = 3.32$), pollution of water sources ($\bar{X} = 3.25$) and pollution of farm land ($\bar{X} = 3.24$) constitute the first ten most serious constraints to women participation in livelihood activities in the two states. These factors exposed by this study are strict and may have unenthusiastic influence in the participation of women in livelihood activities, hence the consequential low participation of women in some of the economic activities in the study area. For example inability to access credit facilities, limited access to farm land, high rate of inflation, indiscriminate changes in

government policies, inadequate supply of electricity and pollution of water sources will limit a poor woman from undertaking high-risk economic ventures like commercial fish farming, poultry, piggery, transportation no matter how profitable they are. This finding was supported by Odinwa et al. (2020) who remarked that asset-poor women cannot enter into high-risk economic activities like fish farming, food processing, poultry and piggery production because they do not own enough (and do not have access to credit) to deal with such ventures. The results clearly indicated that the constraints to women participation in livelihood activities were much more serious in Rivers State with grand mean ($\bar{X} = 3.49$) than in Imo State ($\bar{X} = 2.70$).

Table 4: Constraints to Women’s Participation in Livelihood Activities in Rivers and Imo States

	Rivers	State	Imo	State	Grand		
Constraints	Weighted Score	Mean	Weighted Score	Mean	Total Score	Grand Mean	Remark
	n = 207		n = 207		N = 414		
Unavailability of farm land to women	778	3.76	683	3.30	1461	3.53	Serious
Pollution of farm land	820	3.96	523	2.53	1343	3.24	Serious
Pollution of water sources	801	3.87	546	2.64	1347	3.25	Serious
Indiscriminate bush burning	808	3.90	503	2.43	1311	3.17	Serious
Inability to access credits	804	3.88	610	2.95	1414	3.42	Serious
Inability to access	801	3.87	467	2.26	1268	3.06	

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markets for inputs and outputs							Serious
Indiscriminate changes in government policies	797	3.85	608	2.94	1405	3.39	Serious
Pollution of forests	812	3.92	470	2.27	1282	3.10	Serious
Size of enterprise	777	3.75	524	2.53	1301	3.14	Serious
Effect of drought on crop	745	3.60	519	2.51	1264	3.05	Serious
Over flooding of fish ponds	727	3.51	522	2.52	1249	3.02	Serious
Lack of labour skills	700	3.38	493	2.38	1193	2.88	Serious
Bad road network	707	3.42	524	2.53	1231	2.97	Serious
Poor education	694	3.35	629	3.04	1323	3.20	Serious
Inadequate supply of electricity	720	3.48	590	2.85	1310	3.16	Serious
Death of heads of households	715	3.45	589	2.85	1304	3.15	Serious
Un-readiness to take risks	729	3.52	527	2.55	1256	3.03	Serious
Household size	706	3.41	551	2.66	1257	3.04	Serious
Lack of skills	706	3.41	528	2.55	1234	2.98	Serious
Poor health care system	695	3.36	547	2.64	1242	3.00	Serious
Food insecurity/malnutrition	663	3.20	541	2.61	1204	2.91	Serious
Flooding attacks leading to displacement in places of business	658	3.18	500	2.42	1158	2.80	Serious
Political intervention	658	3.18	530	2.56	1188	2.87	Serious
Widowhood practices	642	3.10	558	2.70	1200	2.90	Serious
Inability to participate in	694	3.35	517	2.50	1211	2.93	Serious

decision making							
Over-reliance of households on source of livelihood	687	3.32	524	2.53	1211	2.93	Serious
No sustainability of means of livelihood	710	3.43	562	2.71	1272	3.07	Serious
Inability to save for expansion of business enterprise	687	3.32	554	2.68	1241	3.00	Serious
Women's attitude to livelihood activities	703	3.40	639	3.09	1342	3.24	Serious
Ban on importation of food items	733	3.54	690	3.33	1423	3.44	Serious
Poverty	754	3.64	633	3.06	1387	3.35	Serious
Lack of power to make decisions	735	3.55	650	3.14	1385	3.35	Serious
Lack of social capital/network	723	3.49	651	3.14	1374	3.32	Serious
Poor housing	723	3.49	580	2.80	1303	3.15	Serious
Poor telecommunication	603	2.91	513	2.48	1116	2.70	Serious
Social restiveness	705	3.41	487	2.35	1192	2.88	Serious
Conflict	706	3.41	542	2.62	1248	3.01	Serious
Inadequate sanitation facilities	685	3.31	535	2.58	1220	2.95	Serious
Kidnapping	702	3.39	540	2.61	1242	3.00	Serious
Theft/armed robbery attacks	718	3.47	566	2.73	1284	3.10	Serious
Poor cooperative societies	700	3.38	537	2.59	1237	2.99	Serious
High rates and taxation	695	3.36	585	2.83	1280	3.09	Serious
High rate of inflation	699	3.38	683	3.30	1382	3.34	Serious
Grand Mean		3.49		2.70		3.10	Serious

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Decision Mean = 2.50

The test of significance on the constraints to women participation in livelihood activities in the Niger Delta Region showed z-calculated (0.02) and z-tabulated (1.96) at less than 0.05% probability level. Since z-calculated is less than z-tabulated, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) which states that ‘The Constraints to women’s

participation in livelihood activities in Rivers and Imo States do not differ significantly’ was established, meaning that the differences in the means of the women in the two states was not significantly different, another indication that women in the Niger Delta region are facing similar challenges that require similar attention to settle in the area.

Table 5: z- Test on the Constraints to Women’s Participation in Livelihood Activities in Rivers and Imo States

Source	N	Mean	df	Variance/Sd	z-cal	z- tab	Remark
Rivers	207	162.69	512	127.24/11.28	0.02	1.96	NS
Imo	207	127.09		1150.32/33.92			
Total	414						

Source: Field Survey, 2025

NS - means Not significant at $P > 0.05\%$

Conclusion

The findings of the study showed equal participation of Rivers and Imo women in livelihood activities for poverty alleviation as test of significance indicated no significant difference. It showcased that they participated highly in crop farming, food vending, trading on agricultural produce and processing of foods, followed by livestock farming, trading on non-agricultural produce, fashion and designing and fish farming among other measured livelihood activities in the two states. The study revealed that the women in both states face common challenges including: unavailability of farm land to women, ban on importation of economic goods, inability to access credits, indiscriminate changes in government policies, poor health services, lack of power to make decisions, high rate of inflation, lack of social capital/network, pollution of water sources and

pollution of farm land which constitute the first ten most serious constraints beside other impediments to women participation in livelihood activities in Rivers and Imo States, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Women should be supported and encouraged by the three tiers of government in both states to actively participate in livelihood economic activities in the area.
2. Women in the Niger Delta Region should not limit themselves to feminine activities only, but should diversify to other lucrative areas of the economy like men to survive,
3. Assets of land, credits, electricity and extension services should be made available and accessible to women in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria by the government and non-

governmental organizations operating in the Niger Delta, and

4. Women in the Niger Delta Region should be determined to form themselves into

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